

The pH of the coloured solution after the formation of the precipitate was found to be between 5.5–5.8. Increase in intensity of the colour by addition of malonyldihydrazide was supposed to be due to the formation of $[\text{Zn}(\text{MDH})_2]_2 \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{NO} \cdot \text{SO}_3$. Following the described procedure, semi quantitative determination of sulphites in water is possible by comparing the colour of the precipitate produced by varying amounts of sulphites (0.1 to 2 ppm) with that produced by the unknown. Further studies to establish this reported reagent system as an absorbing reagent for sulphurdioxide are being pursued.

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References

1. I. M. KOLTHOFF, P. J. ELVING and F. H. STROSS, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1971, p. 48.
2. F. A. PATTY, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", 2nd revised Edn., Vol. II, Interscience, New York, 1968, p. 71.
3. C. BODEKER, *Ann.*, 1981, 117, 183.
4. J. NAIR and V. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 841.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Aromatic Amines Using Catechol and Iodine

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A new spectrophotometric method for the assay of primary and secondary aromatic amines with catechol-iodine reagent at pH 2.6 ± 0.6 has been developed. It is based on the development of purple-red colour of maximum absorbance (λ_{max} 500-520 nm) within 5-20 min (depending on the amine) after mixing with the reagent. The colour is stable for 2 hr. The method is simple, reproducible and accurate within $\pm 1.0\%$. It has been extended to the determination of drugs in pure and dosage forms which either contain a free primary aromatic amino group (sulpha drugs, local anaesthetics, dapsone) or release it through hydrolysis (succinyl sulphathiazole) or reduction (chloramphenicol or folic acid).

Experimental

The absorbance measurements were made with Shimadzu UV 140 double beam spectrophotometer

with 1 cm glass cells. The pH of the solution was adjusted to the desired value using an Elico model LI-120 digital pH meter. A freshly prepared 0.1% aqueous solution of catechol was used. Glycine-HCl (pH 1.0-2.1) and potassium acid phthalate-HCl buffers were prepared according to the procedures given by Lurie¹. All the other reagents used were of analytical grade.

General procedure : To a 25 ml flask, 15 ml of potassium acid phthalate buffer pH 3.1, 1 ml of 0.1% catechol, 1 ml of 0.01 N iodine and 1-5 ml of aromatic amine (concentration range, Table 1) were added in the given order. The solution was then diluted to the mark and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5-30 min (depending on the amine). At the end of this period, the absorbance was read at 500-520 nm against a reagent blank. The aromatic amine concentration was read from a calibration curve prepared with the same compound under identical conditions.

Procedure for compounds which yield primary aromatic amino group on hydrolysis : About 25 mg of the sample was boiled with 20 ml 6 N HCl for 1 hr under reflux, cooled and the excess hydrochloric acid removed under vacuum. The residue was dissolved in 50 ml of warm water and diluted to 250 ml after adjusting the pH to 5.0-7.0. The general procedure was then followed.

Procedure for compounds which yield a primary arylamino group on reduction : About 25 mg of the sample was treated with 25 ml 4 N HCl and 0.75 g zinc dust added in portions. After standing for 1 hr at room temperature, the solution was filtered through cotton wool, the residue was washed with water, excess HCl was removed and diluted to 250 ml after adjusting the pH to 5.0-7.0. The general procedure was then followed.

The sampling and preliminary treatment of dosage forms such as tablets and capsules was performed according to reported procedures^{2,3} and the assays were carried out as above depending on the nature of the compound.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves : The absorbance curves of reagent, primary arylamines and N-methylaniline show maximum absorbance at 500-520 nm; whereas catechol-iodine or primary arylamine-iodine show practically no absorption. The maximum intensity of the colour is developed within 5-20 min and is stable for 2 hr.

Effect of pH : The optimum pH range for complete colour development is 2.0-3.1 with all aromatic amines. Above pH 7.0, the colour begins to fade slowly. All studies are confined to pH 3.0 ± 0.1 .

Amount of catechol : 0.5-1.5 ml of 0.1% catechol solution is required for maximum colour development. 1 ml of 0.1% catechol was used.

Effect of oxidizing agent : A study was made of the use of various oxidizing solutions to be employed in the formation of the coloured species with catechol and aromatic amines. It was found that iron(III) (1 ml ; 0.02 M), sodium metaperiodate (1 ml ; 0.01 M), ammonium vanadate (2 ml ; 0.01N), chromium(VI) (1 ml ; 0.05 N), cerium(IV) (2 ml ; 0.01 N), hexacyanoferrate(III) (2 ml ; 0.01N) or iodine (1 ml ; 0.01N) was necessary for complete colour development. If hydrogen peroxide is used, the experimental conditions are to be modified (catechol, 2 ml of 0.5% ; hydrogen peroxide, 1 ml of 1.8 N ; pH 2.1) and the time taken for complete colour development is 30-50 min. Of these oxidising agents, iodine was preferred as it gave maximum colour development within 5-20 min possessing considerable stability.

Effect of the order of addition : The order of addition of reagents does not have any influence on the colour development, if mixing is carried out immediately or adding catechol at the end even after 30 min. However, any delay in mixing aromatic amine to catechol-iodine reagent causes considerable decrease in absorbance.

Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity values and % recoveries are given in Table 1. The values obtained by the proposed method and the Bratton-Marshall method for dosage forms are given in Table 2. Ten replicate determinations were made with a typical aromatic amine (aniline) and the

TABLE 1—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ASSAY OF AROMATIC AMINES

Amine	Beer's Law limits µg/25 ml	Molar absorp- tivity at 520 nm 1 mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁻³	Recovery %
Aniline	25-150	4.1	99.4
o-Toluidine	50-250	2.9	99.8
p-Toluidine	50-300	3.2	99.1
p-Chloroaniline	50-300	4.4	98.4
p-Nitroaniline	50-250	3.4	97.9
Sulphanilic acid	50-200	4.7	99.7
p-Aminobenzoic acid	50-300	4.1	100.1
p-Phenetidine	50-300	4.6	99.3
Sulphanilamide	50-200	4.3	99.7
Sulphaacetamide	50-200	4.3	100.4
Sulphadimidine	50-200	4.5	99.8
Sulphamerazine	50-200	4.6	99.4
Sulphathiazole	50-200	4.9	99.3
Sulphamoxole	50-200	4.8	99.8
Sulphasomidine	50-200	3.7	99.4
Sulphamethiazole	50-200	4.7	99.5
Sulpha phenazole	50-250	4.9	99.6
Sulphamethoxazole	50-150	4.6	100.2
Sulphapyridine	50-200	4.8	99.7
Benzocaine	50-200	5.0	99.9
Procaine	50-300	4.2	98.9
Dapsone	50-250	8.9	99.2
α-Naphthylamine	50-200	2.9	98.8
β-Naphthylamine	50-300	4.6	99.1
N-Methylaniline	25-100	4.2	99.5
Succinyl sulphathiazole*	50-150	2.9	100.3
Chloramphenicol**	50-200	3.1	100.5
Folic acid***	50-150	2.8	100.8

*After hydrolysis. **After reduction. *** After reduction and applying suitable correction for free amine and using p-amino benzoic acid as standard.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF PHARMACEUTICAL AROMATIC AMINES IN DOSAGE FORMS

Dosage form	Nominal content. g	Proposed method	Found, g Bratton-Marshall method
<i>Tablets</i>			
Sulphadimidine, I.P.	0.500	0.493	0.495
Madribon-Sulphadimethoxine, B.P.	0.500	0.487	0.491
Lederkyn-Sulphamethoxy pyridiazine, B.P.	0.500	0.502	0.508
Sulphapyridine, B.P.	0.500	0.485	0.493
Sulphamox-Sulphamoxole, B.P.	0.500	0.481	0.486
Elkosin-Sulphasomidine, B.P.	0.500	0.494	0.498
Thiazole-Phthalyl sulphathiazole, I.P.	0.500	0.476	0.484
Folic acid, I.P.	0.050	0.048	0.047
<i>Capsules</i>			
Chloramphenicol, I.P.	0.250	0.244	0.246
<i>Eye drops</i>			
Albucid-sulphacetamide sodium, I.P.	1.420	1.38	1.40

relative standard deviation was found to be 0.4%. The advantage of this new method is that it works with most of the dosage forms of aromatic amines and the results obtained are reproducible. Excipients and adjuncts usually present in dosage forms do not interfere. The other nitrogen bearing compounds such as aliphatic amines (primary, secondary and tertiary), cyclohexylamine, benzylamine, diphenylamine, 4-aminophenazone and N,N-dimethylaniline do not respond to the method.

Interferences : The following amounts (ppm) of other constituents usually present in dosage forms are found to give less than 3% error in the determination of aromatic amines (e.g. sulphathiazole) : talc (250), magnesium stearate (300), calcium phosphate (200), sodium chloride (350), chloramphenicol (250), penicillins (250), tetracycline (60), streptomycin (150), glucose (500) and trimethoprim (10%).

Mechanism : Titrimetric studies to know the reactivity of iodine separately with catechol and aromatic amine (sulphanilamide) at pH 3.1 revealed that iodine reacts almost completely within 15 min with catechol, whereas it does not react at all with sulphanilamide even after 1 hr. It is well known that oxidation of catechol under acidic conditions with oxidizing agents takes place in two steps, each involving removal of one electron, first to the semiquinone (purple-red colour) then to the o-benzoquinone^{4,5}. If catechol-iodine reagent is replaced by o-benzoquinone in the general procedure, development of purple-red colour does not take place indicating that o-benzoquinone is not involved. Probably the intermediate semiquinone (because of resonance stabilisation, possesses longer life time and do not tend to attack the solvent or to initiate olefinic polymerisation) interacts with aromatic amine for the colour development. The composition of the coloured species formed between catechol (excess)-iodine reagent (semiquinone) and primary aromatic amine was determined spectrophotometrically using Job's continuous variation

and slope ratio methods. These methods show that iodine and primary arylamine combine in a 2:1 molar ratio. The failure in getting colour in alkaline pH clearly rules out the possibility of oxidative coupling between aromatic amine and catechol and so it is regarded as charge-transfer complex. The charge transfer may be presumed to be taking place involving electron-transfer from the highest occupied π molecular orbital of the primary arylamine to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, π^* , of the semiquinone radicals as in the case of metol NBS reagent⁶.

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References

1. JU. LURIE, "Hand Book of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1975, p. 255.
2. T. HIGUCHI and H. E. BROCHMANN, "Pharmaceutical Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1961, p. 187.
3. M. M. AMER and M. I. WALASH, *Bull. Fac. Pharm. Cairo*, 1973, **2**, 161.
4. S. W. WEIDMAN and E. T. KAISER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 5820.
5. J. C. P. SMITH and A. CARRINGTON, *Mol. Phys.*, 1967, **12**, 439.
6. C. S. PRAKASA SASTRY, B. G. RAO and B. S. REDDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 655.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium with Rubeanic Acid in Presence of Piperidine, Quinoline, α -Picoline and Collidine

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RUBEANIC acid in conjunction with different organic heterocyclic bases have been utilised to estimate Pd, Co and Ni^{1,5-7}. It has been found that piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline and collidine also enhance the colour and solubility of Pd(II) complex of rubeanic acid as a result of which rubeanic acid and one of the above four heterocyclic aromatic bases make a suitable ligand pair for the determination of palladium spectrophotometrically. Among the four bases studied, collidine is found to form the most effective ligand pair with rubeanic acid, the molar extinction coefficient in this case being distinctly higher than in other systems. The yellow colours which are developed

in the above four systems have been found to absorb maximally at 380 nm in case of piperidine and quinoline and at 410 nm in case of α -picoline and collidine. The optimum pH range has been found to be 7-10.5 in each of the four systems where Beer's Law is obeyed.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and apparatus: Palladium solution was standardised by dimethylglyoxime. A 0.1% solution of rubeanic acid was prepared in 95% ethyl alcohol. The solution was found to remain stable for several days. 10% solution of each, in distilled ethanol, were obtained from freshly distilled piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline and collidine (analytical grade).

All absorbance measurements were made with a Hilger-UVispek spectrophotometer. The pH values are determined with an Elico Model LI-10 pH meter, the later values being with respect to aqueous alcoholic solution.

Procedure: To a slightly acidic solution of palladium, free from interfering ions, 1 ml reagent solution (0.1% w/v) was added after the addition of any of the four bases for determinations with piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline or collidine. 2 ml piperidine, 5 ml quinoline, 3 ml α -picoline and 2 ml collidine were added before the addition of the reagent. The final volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled alcohol and the absorbance measured at 380 nm for piperidine and quinoline and at 410 nm for α -picoline and collidine. The results of the above investigations are represented in Table 1.

Composition of the complexes: The composition of the complexes as determined by Job's method of continued variation⁸ and molar ratio method⁹ shows that there are two different species with different heterocyclic base systems. While with pyridine and collidine, the presence of 1:1 metal:rubeanic acid ratio is observed, the 1:2 system seems to be predominant in other three systems (piperidine and rubeanic acid, quinoline and rubeanic acid and α -picoline and rubeanic acid). Bobtelsky and Eisenstadter⁹ found by heterometric titration and micro analysis of the dried product that palladium combines with rubeanic acid to afford a number of compounds having the composition Pd₂Rba₂, PdRba, Pd₂Rba₂ and PdRba₂ (where Rba=rubeanic acid molecule or its radical) depending on the pH of the medium during precipitation and the amount of reagent present⁹. In the present case the units containing one Pd ion (1:1 and 1:2 variety) seems to be stabilised by the additional ligation of heterocyclic bases.

The results of Job's method and molar ratio method of the four systems are represented graphically (Figs. 1-8).